

Updating and Improving Statistical Methods for Evaluating the Quality of Travel Based on the Distribution of Defects in Road Pavements

*Atualização e Aprimoramento de Métodos Estatísticos para
Avaliação da Qualidade de Viagem com Base na Distribuição de
Defeitos em Pavimentos Rodoviários*
*Actualización y Mejora de los Métodos Estadísticos para Evaluar la
Calidad de los Desplazamientos a partir de la Distribución de
Defectos en los Pavimentos de las Carreteras*

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Abstract:

This paper proposes a methodological update for assessing travel quality on highways based on the relationship between the distribution of pavement surface distresses and scores assigned by trained evaluators. Using data collected from 37 rural highway segments in São Paulo, Brazil, multiple linear regression and classification scales based on the normal distribution were applied. The results indicate that perceived travel quality can be reliably estimated from objective distress variables. Improvements to the original method are suggested, including the incorporation of machine learning techniques and expanded cross-regional data validation. It is concluded that the integration of subjective and objective data can guide maintenance priorities and improve the efficiency of road infrastructure management.

Keywords: *Travel quality, pavement distress, multiple regression, Likert scales, infrastructure management.*

Resumo:

Este artigo propõe uma atualização metodológica para a avaliação da qualidade de viagem em rodovias, com base na relação entre a distribuição de defeitos superficiais do pavimento e notas atribuídas por avaliadores treinados. Utilizando dados coletados em 37 segmentos rodoviários vicinais no estado de São Paulo, aplicaram-se técnicas de regressão linear múltipla e análise de escalas de classificação baseadas na distribuição normal. Os resultados indicam que é possível estimar a qualidade percebida da viagem a partir de variáveis objetivas de defeitos, com confiabilidade estatística. São sugeridas melhorias no método original, incluindo a incorporação de técnicas de machine learning e a expansão da base de dados para validação cross-regional. Conclui-se que a integração de dados subjetivos e objetivos pode orientar prioridades de manutenção e melhorar a eficiência na gestão de infraestrutura rodoviária.

Palavras-chave: Qualidade de viagem, defeitos de pavimento, regressão múltipla, escalas de Likert, gestão de infraestrutura.

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Este artículo propone una actualización metodológica para evaluar la calidad de los viajes en las carreteras a partir de la relación entre la distribución de las dificultades de la superficie del pavimento y los puntajes asignados por evaluadores capacitados. Utilizando datos recolectados de 37 tramos de carreteras rurales en São Paulo, Brasil, se aplicaron escalas de regresión lineal múltiple y clasificación basadas en la distribución normal. Los resultados indican que la calidad percibida del viaje se puede estimar de manera confiable a partir de variables objetivas de angustia. Se sugieren mejoras al método original, incluida la incorporación de técnicas de aprendizaje automático y la validación de datos interregional ampliada. Se concluye que la integración de datos subjetivos y objetivos puede orientar las prioridades de mantenimiento y mejorar la eficiencia de la gestión de la infraestructura vial.

Palabras clave: *Calidad de viaje, deterioro del pavimento, regresión múltiple, escalas Likert, gestión de infraestructuras.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The quality of road travel is influenced by multiple factors, among which pavement surface conditions stand out. Defects such as cracks, potholes, patches, and deformations directly affect users' comfort and safety (Haas, Hudson & Zaniewski, 1994). Traditionally, the evaluation of these conditions has been carried out through visual and instrumental inspections, but incorporating user perception has gained prominence in international literature (Al-Omari & Darter, 1994; Gulen et al., 1994).

Daroncho's original work (2001) explored the relationship between defect distribution and scores assigned by trained raters, using multiple linear regression and rating scales. However, recent advances in statistical and machine learning techniques offer opportunities to improve the accuracy and applicability of this method.

Remote sensing techniques, including high-resolution drone imagery and LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) scanning and ranging, now enable comprehensive, frequent capture of pavement condition data (Cursino, Machado, 2021). Simultaneously, artificial intelligence algorithms, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have demonstrated superior capabilities in the automatic detection and classification of pavement defects (Sholevar, Golroo, Esfahani, 2022). These emerging technologies offer opportunities to overcome limitations of traditional methods, such as subjectivity in visual assessment and low inspection frequency.

This article aims to revisit and update Daroncho's (2001) methodology, incorporating new statistical approaches and proposing an expanded framework for data collection and analysis. Additionally, it discusses the feasibility of applying the method in diverse contexts and its integration with pavement management systems.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. RIDE QUALITY AND PAVEMENT DEFECTS

The quality of the ride is a multidimensional construct that encompasses comfort, safety, and efficiency (Haas & Hudson, 1996). Surface pavement defects, such as cracks, potholes, and deformations, are objective indicators that correlate users' subjective perceptions (SHRP, 1993; Austroads, 1987).

2.2. SUBJECTIVE AND OBJECTIVE ASSESSMENT METHODS

The trained-evaluator panel approach was pioneered by AASHO (1962) and later consolidated by Carey and Irick (1960). More recently, this method has been gradually replaced by automated approaches. Singh et al. (2022) demonstrated that computer vision-based systems can achieve 95% accuracy in crack detection, significantly surpassing human evaluation in terms of consistency and speed.

2.3. REMOTE SENSING IN TRANSPORTATION INFRASTRUCTURE

Drone and LiDAR applications for road infrastructure monitoring have expanded rapidly since 2020. Zhang, Chen, Wu, Guo, Jia (2021) developed an integrated drone- LiDAR system that captures high-precision 3D data for surface deformation assessment, while Kothai, Prabakaran, Srinivasa Murthy, Cenkeramaddi, Kakani et al. (2024) proposed a comprehensive systematic review on automated techniques for detecting, classifying, and analyzing pavement damage based on artificial intelligence algorithms (machine learning and deep learning).

2.4. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PAVEMENT MANAGEMENT

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2.5. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PAVEMENT MANAGEMENT

Advances in deep learning have revolutionized the analysis of infrastructure data. Deng, Li, Zhou, ZHANG, Yang, Shang Li (2023) applied recurrent neural networks to predict the evolution of defects over time, while Paraschos, Geronikos, Kepaptsoglou and Koulouriotis (2025) developed a methodology based on reinforcement learning (RL) to optimize pavement maintenance planning.

3. METHOD

3.1. DATA COLLECTION

Original data from 37 segments of secondary roads near Araraquara, SP, collected between January and March 2001, were used. The variables included:

- Scores assigned by 32 trained evaluators (scale 1–5);
- Measurements and counts of 31 types of defects, classified by severity.

3.2. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

- Stepwise Multiple Linear Regression: to identify significant variables for predicting grades.
- Likert scale: to transform grades into z-scores and compare distributions.
- Hypothesis testing: comparison of means using Student's t-test.

3.3. PROPOSED UPDATE

- Incorporation of neural or random networks for nonlinear modeling.
- Expanding the sample with data from multiple regions.
- Using digital images and sensors to automate the collection of defective data.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION

The regression model explained 70.83% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.7083$), with five significant variables (Table 1).

Tabela 1: Coeficientes significativos do modelo de regressão

Variable	Coefficient	p-value
Interceptor	3,51144	< 0,001
Patch (medium severity)	-0,00079	0,046
Wear and tears (medium severity)	-0,00058	0,019
Patch (high severity)	-0,00071	0,032
Fatigue crack (medium severity)	-0,00073	0,015
Step on the shoulder of the road	0,00473	0,029

Source: Daroncho (2001)

4.2. RATING SCALES

The scales derived from z-scores showed agreement between assigned and estimated scores ($t = 0.1556$, $p > 0.05$), validating the method's consistency.

4.3. PROPOSAL FOR ADVANCED MODELING

It is suggested that machine learning algorithms be applied, along with the use of drones (LiDAR), to automatically identify defects in 3D. This would enable capturing non-linear relationships and interactions among variables, as well as using computer vision for automatic defect classification. This action would eliminate the need for users to assign ratings, allowing the tool to be trained and subsequently calibrated at specific times.

5. CONCLUSION

The method proposed by Daroncho (2001) proved robust for estimating ride quality based on pavement defects. Updating it with modern data analysis techniques could broaden its applicability and accuracy. It is recommended:

- Cross -regional validation with expanded samples;
- Integration with pavement management systems;
- Automation of defect collection and classification via sensors and AI.

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